

A Knowledge-Driven Scheduling Architecture Integrated with a Digital Twin

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Abstract

Modern manufacturing systems operate under high variability, uncertainty, and reduced decision time, which limits the applicability of classical optimisation and static heuristic scheduling approaches. This paper proposes a knowledge-driven scheduling architecture integrated with a digital twin to support adaptive decision-making in dynamic production environments. The framework combines context-sensitive strategy restriction, multi-criteria evaluation, and simulation-based validation within a closed-loop structure. Scheduling strategies are dynamically selected and ranked based on real-time system conditions, and validated through high-fidelity digital twin simulations prior to deployment. A formal mathematical model of the architecture is presented. The proposed architecture establishes a foundation for future empirical validation in industrial environments.

Keywords

Operations Scheduling, Artificial Intelligence, Digital Twin, Knowledge-based scheduling, Smart Manufacturing

1 Introduction

Operations scheduling allocates limited resources to tasks over time while satisfying technological and operational constraints and optimising performance objectives. It is a central decision-making problem in manufacturing, logistics, and service operations. Many scheduling problems, including job shop and flexible job shop scheduling problems, are NP-hard, making exact optimisation computationally infeasible for large industrial instances. Contemporary manufacturing environments exhibit high product variability, shorter life cycles, frequent disturbances, flexible routing, and increasing automation. Under these conditions, scheduling shifts from an offline planning activity to a real-time control function. Reduced decision time and rising system complexity shift attention from generating optimal schedules to identifying robust, adaptable solutions. Traditional approaches such as mathematical programming, dispatching rules, and metaheuristics face well-known limitations. Exact methods scale poorly, static rules lack contextual adaptability, and metaheuristics often require extensive computation or parameter tuning. Consequently, recent research emphasises adaptive, data-driven, and simulation-supported scheduling methods. Digital twins and artificial intelligence (AI) have emerged as key enablers of intelligent, responsive scheduling systems (Serrano-Ruiz et al., 2021; Negri et al., 2021). Despite progress, several challenges persist. Many AI-based approaches rely either on generative optimisation or purely data-driven learning, often without incorporating structured domain knowledge. Simulation and scheduling are frequently treated as loosely coupled components, and interpretability remains limited an important issue in industrial environments where transparency and controllability are essential.

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To address these limitations, this paper proposes a knowledge-driven scheduling architecture integrated with a digital twin. The approach combines hierarchical rule-based knowledge representation, context-sensitive strategy restriction, and simulation-based validation within a closed-loop control framework. The system dynamically selects and ranks scheduling strategies based on the current production state and evaluates candidate solutions through digital-twin simulations before deployment.

The main contributions of this paper are:

- the integration of structured domain knowledge and digital twin simulation into a unified scheduling decision loop.
- the formulation of a mathematical model describing the interaction between monitoring, strategy selection, simulation, and multi-criteria evaluation layers.
- the design of a modular architecture supporting adaptive scheduling in dynamic manufacturing environments.

2 State of the Art

The application of AI in scheduling was also supported by the fact that the difficult, complex scheduling problem becomes even more challenging in adaptive manufacturing systems (AMS) due to reduced decision time and increased problem complexity (Serrano-Ruiz et al., 2021). The high frequency of changes in running production, frequent failures, and drastic reductions in setup times reduce the available time for decision preparation. The possibility of variable technological processes, the interchangeability of machines, the automation of transport and handling operations, and the limited number of tools, pallets, and fixtures have increased the complexity of the scheduling problem. Under such conditions, the problem shifts from the search for optimal solutions to the identification of admissible and robust schedules (Fu et al., 2021). The rapid evolution of adaptive manufacturing environments reduces the direct transferability of traditional experiential knowledge, thereby increasing the need for computational decision support systems. A possible solution is the use of computer-based decision support systems, either in the form of a support tool for human subject decisions, the so-called decision support systems or full equivalent substitution of a human by a program system. The degree of substitution of a human by an AI in the scheduling process depends on several factors. One of the main ones is the degree of automation of the production environment and control functions. In general, the higher the degree of automation in the production process, the higher the degree of automation in the scheduling process (Marzia et al., 2023). Interactive systems seem better suited to traditional workshops, significantly improving efficiency and facilitating human decision-making. On the contrary, for highly automated AMS, designs of autonomous systems often prevail as part of a control system or control hierarchy (short-term planning - scheduling - real-time control) (Destouet et al., 2023). Overall, recent research indicates a shift: scheduling is increasingly moving towards real-time activities, i.e., from the planning horizon to the control horizon (S. Zhang et al., 2021).

2.1 Generative vs. Evaluative AI in Scheduling

According to the way artificial intelligence is applied in scheduling, two main approaches can be distinguished: generative and evaluative systems.

Generative systems apply AI principles to directly create a schedule by exploring the state space or by reasoning within defined constraints. In such systems, artificial intelligence replaces traditional algorithmic procedures used for schedule generation. While generative AI-based scheduling approaches have demonstrated promising results, their deployment in complex industrial environments remains relatively limited compared to hybrid or simulation-supported

approaches. The most successful applications have been reported at higher levels of planning, such as rough production scheduling. Many generative systems are implemented as planning expert systems that rely on forward-chaining inference mechanisms.

Evaluative systems, in contrast, apply AI principles in several complementary roles:

- to evaluate alternative schedule variants and select the most appropriate one,
- to determine suitable models, methods, or rules for schedule generation,
- to correct, improve, and maintain already created schedules.

In evaluative approaches, the schedule itself is generated algorithmically, for example using operations research methods, heuristic procedures, or simulation models. Artificial intelligence techniques are then applied to analyse, evaluate, or improve the generated solutions (Del Gallo et al., 2023). Consequently, evaluative systems represent a hybrid approach that combines artificial intelligence with conventional optimisation and simulation methods.

2.2 Digital Twins in Scheduling

Digital twins have become a key element of modern planning. They allow the creation of high-fidelity virtual models of manufacturing systems that are synchronized with real-world data. This allows testing different planning strategies, assessing their robustness, and analyzing system behavior under uncertainty (Tliba et al., 2022). Simheuristic approaches combine optimization with digital twins, thereby increasing adaptability and fault tolerance (Negri et al., 2021).

2.3 Trends in Scheduling Research

Operations research is moving towards energy-efficient and multi-objective models that consider a wider range of performance criteria (Gahm et al., 2016; F. Zhang et al., 2024). At the same time, decentralized and multi-agent solutions are gaining importance, enabling adaptive production control when combined with digital twins (Siatras et al., 2024; Peng et al., 2024).

Despite progress, integrating structured domain knowledge, hierarchical inference, and digital twins into a unified decision-making framework remains underexplored. Overall, the literature demonstrates a clear transition from static, optimisation-centric scheduling to adaptive, simulation-supported, and AI-driven frameworks. Digital twin technologies enable virtual validation of candidate schedules, while data-driven and multi-agent approaches enhance responsiveness in dynamic environments. However, the explicit integration of structured domain knowledge, hierarchical rule-based reasoning, and digital twin simulation within a unified closed-loop architecture remains insufficiently formalised. This gap motivates the architecture presented in this paper.

3 Proposed Scheduling Architecture

The proposed architecture of the Integrated Scheduling System (ISS) combines artificial intelligence, structured knowledge, and simulation through a digital twin. The goal is to enable dynamic adaptation of scheduling decisions in an environment with high uncertainty and changing loads. The ISS can generate, evaluate, and compare multiple scheduling scenarios, using known heuristics (e.g., priority rules) and their context-sensitive combinations. In line with Vespoli et al. (2021) and Serôdio et al. (2024), the architecture enables predictive data processing and rapid response to changes in the system.

ISS is designed as a closed control loop consisting of four layers:

- Monitoring Layer

- Knowledge-Based Strategy Selection Layer
- Digital Twin Simulation Layer
- Evaluation and Adaptation Layer

Together, these layers create an adaptive mechanism that first limits the space of possible strategies, then simulates them, evaluates them, and selects the most suitable one for real deployment.

3.1 Monitoring Layer

The Monitoring Layer connects the physical production system to the ISS's digital decision-making core. Its task is to:

- obtain current data on the state of production,
- filter and synchronize information,
- create an accurate representation of the state of the system for further decision-making.

The quality of scheduling decisions depends directly on the accuracy and timeliness of this state representation.

The physical production system includes:

- Machines $M = \{M_1, \dots, M_m\}$
- Jobs $J = \{J_1, \dots, J_n\}$
- Resources and transport systems
- IoT sensing infrastructure

The real system state at time t including machine availability, queue lengths, job attributes, due dates, and resource status, is represented as:

$$x_{\text{real}}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n \quad (1)$$

Real-time data are processed and synchronized:

$$x_{\text{real}}(t) \rightarrow x_{\text{sync}}(t) \quad (2)$$

This layer ensures consistency between physical and virtual representations. Functional components of the Monitoring Layer include:

- Data Acquisition Module, which collects data from IoT sensors, PLC systems, MES/ERP systems, machine controllers, etc.
- Data Preprocessing Module, which performs noise filtering, outlier detection and removal, time synchronisation, and missing data imputation.
- State Aggregation Module, which transforms raw data into a compact state vector:

$$x(t) = [m(t), q(t), r(t), d(t), s(t)] \quad (3)$$

where

- $m(t)$ – machine states,
- $q(t)$ – queue lengths,
- $r(t)$ – resource availability,
- $d(t)$ – job due dates,
- $s(t)$ – system-level parameters (load, utilisation).

3.2 Knowledge-Based Strategy Selection Layer

This layer represents the system's symbolic reasoning component. It prevents brute-force search by restricting the strategy space intelligently based on structured domain knowledge.

Its objectives are to:

- restrict the space of available scheduling strategies,
- select relevant strategies according to the current system context,
- rank them according to expected suitability.

Formally, this layer can be modelled as follows: Let:

$$\mathcal{R} = \{\mathcal{R}_1, \mathcal{R}_2, \dots, \mathcal{R}_k\} \quad (4)$$

be the set of all available scheduling strategies, where R_i represents a scheduling rule or strategy.

In the current state of the system, the properties of the production environment impose constraints that can be taken into account when selecting a subset of suitable scheduling strategies. Then the context-restricted strategy subset \mathcal{R}_c can be defined as follows:

$$\mathcal{R}_c(x(t)) \subseteq \mathcal{R} \quad (5)$$

3.3 Digital Twin Simulation Layer

A digital twin is a virtual replica of a physical system (e.g., a factory or production line). Simulations with digital twins enable the testing and optimisation of scheduling strategies before implementation (Serrano-Ruiz et al., 2021; Ouahabi et al., 2024). Here is how:

- *Virtual Representation:* Digital twins are built using real-time and historical data from physical systems, such as production lines, warehouses, or fleets. They replicate the behaviour, constraints, and interdependencies of the physical environment.
- *Simulation of Scenarios:* Scheduling strategies can be tested in the digital twin to evaluate their performance under different scenarios, such as varying workloads, resource availability, or unexpected disruptions (e.g., equipment failure or increased demand).
- *Dynamic Adjustments:* Digital twins can model dynamic systems, such as fluctuating demand or real-time changes, enabling the testing of adaptive scheduling strategies that respond to live data.
- *Performance Analysis:* By running simulations, digital twins help identify bottlenecks, inefficiencies, or conflicts in scheduling strategies, providing insights into areas that need improvement.
- *Optimisation Before Deployment:* Scheduling solutions can be fine-tuned and validated in a virtual environment before deployment in the real world. This minimises risks, reduces costs, and ensures smoother transitions.
- *Predictive Insights:* Digital twins integrate predictive analytics to forecast the outcomes of different scheduling decisions. For example, they can predict delays or resource shortages and recommend proactive adjustments.
- *Continuous Feedback Loop:* As digital twins are connected to the physical system via IoT and real-time data feeds, they update and refine their simulations based on actual outcomes, ensuring ongoing accuracy and relevance.

The digital twin is designed as a cyber-physical closed-loop control system integrating real-time monitoring, knowledge-based decision support, simulation-based evaluation, and adaptive feedback (Ouahabi et al., 2024).

The Digital Twin Simulation Layer acts as a virtual experimentation environment, where candidate schedules are tested before implementation in the real system. This layer transforms scheduling from rule-based selection to simulation-validated decision-making, providing robustness and risk mitigation. The digital twin model can be formally defined as follows:

$$\mathcal{DT} = (X, U, F, G, \mathcal{R}, J) \quad (6)$$

where:

- X – state space,
- U – decision space,
- F – transition function,
- G – performance metrics,
- \mathcal{R} – strategy set,
- J – objective function.

The dynamic model of a digital twin can be defined as follows:

$$x_{DT}(t+1) = F(x_{DT}(t), S_i, \omega(t)) \quad (7)$$

where:

- F represents the production system dynamics,
- S_i is the candidate schedule,
- $\omega(t)$ models stochastic disturbances.

The digital twin includes the following components:

- Discrete-event simulation,
- Machine failure models,
- Sequence-dependent setup modelling,
- Transport system modelling,
- Flexible routing representation,
- Processing time variability modelling.

Parallel Strategy Evaluation can be modelled as follows: For each strategy, the candidate schedule is

$$S_i = \Phi(\mathcal{R}_i, x_{DT}(t)) \quad (8)$$

Simulated evolution is

$$x_{DT}^{(i)}(t+1) = F(x_{DT}(t), S_i) \quad (9)$$

Furthermore, the performance metric is:

$$f_k(S_i) \quad (10)$$

3.4 Evaluation and Adaptation Layer

The ISS evaluates simulated scheduling strategies against predefined criteria. Since it also computes production system and task parameters, multi-criteria evaluation methods can be applied, with the ISS assigning weight coefficients to individual criteria. This evaluation may operate as an external procedural module triggered by production rules. If the results are unsatisfactory, the ISS adjusts task priorities and/or selects alternative scheduling strategies and reruns the simulation. If satisfactory, it selects and deploys the schedule that best meets the defined criteria. Formally, this layer evaluates candidate schedules, selects the best solution, and updates the knowledge structure. When using Multi-Criteria Evaluation

$$J(S_i) = \sum_{k=1}^m w_k f_k(S_i) \quad (11)$$

where

- $J(S_i)$ — multi-criteria objective function for generated schedule S_i ,
- f_k — performance metrics,
- w_k — weight coefficients.

The decision can be selected as follows:

$$S^* = \arg \min_{S_i} J(S_i) \quad (12)$$

Selected schedule:

$$u^*(t) = S^* \quad (13)$$

The selected schedule is deployed in the physical system.

Adaptation mechanisms can be defined as follows:

Strategy ranking update

$$Q(\mathcal{R}_i) \leftarrow Q(\mathcal{R}_i) + \beta(J_{\text{ref}} - J(S_i)) \quad (14)$$

Weight adjustment

$$w_k(t+1) = w_k(t) + \alpha \Delta_k \quad (15)$$

And calibration of Fuzzy Parameters

$$\theta_{\text{new}} = \theta_{\text{old}} + \alpha \Delta \quad (16)$$

The four-layer architecture transforms scheduling from a static rule-application process into a closed-loop, adaptive decision-making framework that integrates real-time monitoring, symbolic knowledge restriction, simulation-based validation, and performance-driven adaptation. The architecture forms a hierarchically organised closed-loop control system (see Figure 1).

4 Implementation and Evaluation

The proposed architecture integrates strategy selection, simulation-based validation, adaptive knowledge improvement, and explanatory capabilities. It supports both industrial deployment and educational use, where it is applied in production management training to model decision-making scenarios and evaluate alternative planning strategies. This proposal builds on the authors' experience implementing scheduling systems for less-automated manufacturing processes using artificial intelligence in the form of expert systems. The architecture will be implemented as a prototype scheduling module.

Figure 1. Architecture of the knowledge-driven scheduling system.

5 Conclusion

This paper presented a knowledge-driven scheduling architecture integrated with a digital twin to support adaptive decision-making in modern manufacturing environments. The proposed framework combines hierarchical knowledge representation, context-sensitive restriction of scheduling strategies, simulation-based validation, and multi-criteria evaluation within a unified closed-loop structure. By embedding structured heuristic knowledge into a simulation-supported decision process, the architecture enables context-aware selection and verification of scheduling strategies prior to their deployment in the physical production system. The integration of a digital twin provides a risk-free environment for evaluating candidate schedules under dynamic and uncertain operating conditions, enabling robustness analysis and proactive adaptation to disturbances. Compared with static rule-based scheduling approaches, the proposed framework introduces adaptive ranking and contextual calibration mechanisms that allow continuous improvement of scheduling performance while maintaining interpretability through explicit knowledge representation. The architecture therefore provides a structured approach to integrating symbolic artificial intelligence methods with simulation-based optimisation for production scheduling. The proposed framework represents a conceptual step toward more adaptive and transparent scheduling systems capable of operating in highly dynamic manufacturing environments. However, several challenges remain. The effectiveness of the approach depends on the fidelity and calibration of the digital twin model, which requires accurate data and domain expertise. Contextual parameters must be calibrated for specific production systems, and scalability may become an issue as the space of scheduling strategies increases. Consequently, further validation in industrial environments is required. Future research will focus on large-scale experimental evaluation, automated calibration of contextual parameters, and the integration of data-driven learning mechanisms for dynamic strategy refinement. Hybrid symbolic–data-driven approaches represent a promising direction for combining interpretability with adaptability in intelligent production scheduling systems.

Resources

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